

Cubosomes-Enabled Theranostics: A Futuristic Approach for Simultaneous Diagnosis and Therapy in Precision Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Over more than two decades, the field of theranostics has evolved as a game-changing strategy in precision medicine, merging diagnostics and therapeutics into one integrated system. Cubosomes, a kind of lipid-based nanoparticle with bicontinuous cubic phases, have drawn a lot of interest for its capacity to encapsulate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds, give prolonged release, and allow for targeted delivery. Their modular structure enables surface functionalisation with ligands or polymers, which improves biocompatibility and site-specific activity. Cubosome-enabled theranostics have shown promise in oncology, cardiovascular disease, and neurological disorders, with improved bioavailability, lower toxicity, and simultaneous monitoring of therapeutic response using multimodal imaging modalities such as MRI, fluorescence imaging, and photothermal/photodynamic techniques. Despite obstacles in large-scale development, stability, and regulatory approval, innovations in nanotechnology, artificial intelligence, and personalised medicine are accelerating their adoption. This review focusses on cubosomes structural properties, functional adaptability, and biological applications, emphasising their potential as smart, patient-specific theranostic platforms.

Keywords: Cubosomes, Theranostics, Precision Medicine, Targeted Drug Delivery, Nanotechnology, Multimodal Imaging

INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, tremendous advances in molecular imaging and biomedical science have had a profound impact on disease detection and treatment. Two rapidly emerging industries that offer a more precise, patient centered approach to healthcare personalized medicine and theranostics are driving this shift. Combining the words "therapy" and "diagnostics," "Theranostics" refers to the use of diagnostic imaging in combination with targeted therapies to help with real-time monitoring, response evaluation, and treatment planning. On the other hand, Personalised medicine seeks to personalise medical treatment to each patient's unique traits, which are frequently determined by metabolic, proteomic, or genetic data.¹ Nanotheranostics is the development of various nanocarriers such as polymer conjugations, dendrimers, micelles, liposomes, metal

and inorganic nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes, and biodegradable polymer nanoparticles for the sustained, controlled, and targeted co-delivery of diagnostic and therapeutic agents for improved theranostics and fewer side effects.²

Theranostic platforms, such as molecular imaging agents, radiopharmaceuticals, and nanoparticle systems, are increasingly being developed with personalised medicine principles in sight. These technologies improve therapeutic efficacy, diminish toxicity, and allow for predictive modelling. Furthermore, the integration of computer modelling, multi-omics data, and machine learning improves our ability to personalise therapy options and improve therapeutic techniques.³

A hexagonal cubic phase liquid crystal disperses to form nanostructured particles known as cubosomes, which are typically stabilised by surfactants such as

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Poloxamer 407. Two non-intersecting yet continuous water channels are formed by their internal architecture, which is a highly organised, three-dimensional periodic minimum surface. Cubosomes with this pattern have a large surface area and can include hydrophilic and hydrophobic substances, such as proteins, imaging agents, and tiny molecules.⁴

Cubosomes have several benefits over conventional nanocarriers in the field of theranostics, including improved bioavailability, regulated drug release, and inherent imaging capabilities when functionalised with fluorophores or contrast agents. A crucial component of precision medicine is cell-specific delivery with few off target effects, which is made possible by their biocompatibility and modular design, which also permit surface alterations with targeting ligands.

The development of cubosome-enabled theranostic platforms for a range of therapeutic indications, including cancer, infectious illnesses, and neurological disorders, has been spurred by recent developments in nanotechnology and imaging modalities. Although its encouraging characteristics, issues including scale-up, long-term stability, and regulatory barriers are still being researched. In addition to showcasing the cubosome-based theranostic systems' promise for personalised treatment in the future, this study attempts to give a through overview of their design, synthesis, characterisation, and biomedical applications.⁵

Figure 1 : Cubosomal Enabled Theranostics

STRUCTURAL AND PHYSIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CUBOSOMES:

DIFFERENT MORPHOLOGY OF CUBIC PHASES:

Internal bicontinuous cubic phases, such as Pn3m (diamond), Im3m (primitive) and Ia3d (gyroid), are characteristics of cubosomes, which are nanostructured lipid carriers. These structures are made up of a honeycomb-like 3D network of lipid bilayers with water channels scattered. A large variety of medicinal and diagnostic substances can be effectively encapsulated due to its dual hydrophilic–hydrophobic domains and remarkably high internal surface area.

Figure 2 : Cubic Phases of Cubosomes

Cubosomes are typically between 100 and 500 nm in size and are stabilised with surfactants including Pluronic F127, which promotes colloidal stability and reduces aggregation. They are made up of amphiphilic lipids, including phytantriol and glycerol monooleate (GMO). Their surface features, like as zeta potential, are capable of being tailored for the best interaction with biological surroundings. The outer layer can be treated by using particular ligands, antibodies, or imaging agents to improve theranostic accuracy.⁶

Cubosomes release encapsulated compounds in a controlled and consistent manner, which is critical for reducing side effects and dosage frequency. Theranostics' features of ongoing therapy and continuous evaluation are also enabled by their ability to co-deliver drugs and imaging agents. Additionally, their internal aqueous channels allow for the incorporation of MRI, CT, or fluorescence contrast agents, while their biocompatibility and biological degradation ensure clinical safety.

COMPONENTS OF CUBOSOMES:

GLYCERYL MONOOLEATE:

GMOs are transparent, polar, unsaturated monoglycerides. Their hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value is three. The most predominant fatty acids in this mixture are monounsaturated fatty acids and oleic acid glycerides. Monooleate is an amorphous lipid that can take on various lyotropic liquid crystal structures. GMOs have both hydrophilic and hydrophobic properties because to the inclusion of hydroxyl groups which can form hydrogen bonds with water in an aqueous solution.

PHYTANTRIOL:

Phytantriol is a synthetic branched-chain lipid that is commonly utilised in the formulation of nanostructured materials liquid crystalline systems, including cubosomes and hexosomes. It is well-known for its outstanding self-assembly behaviour in fluid conditions, resulting in stable two-dimensional cubic phases that do not require additional co-surfactants. When compared to other lipids such as glycerol monooleate (GMO), phytantriol has higher chemical stability as well as resistance to hydrolysis, making it appropriate for long-term storage and drug administration applications. Its biocompatibility, low toxicological profile, and ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds make it an important ingredient in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and theranostic compositions.

STABILIZERS:

Stabilisers are essential in cubosome formulations, as they inhibit aggregation and ensure the long-term stability of these nanostructured phospholipid carriers. They accomplish this by adsorbing to the granular surface, forming a protective coating that prevents particle coalescence. The stabiliser functions as an electric buffer between particles, preventing close contact and maintaining particle stability. Choosing an adequate stabiliser is crucial as it contributes to the lipid water assembly without compromising the cubic liquid crystallinity. Pluronic, particularly F127 (Poloxamer 407), are widely regarded as the "gold standard" stabilising agent.⁷

THERNOSTIC POTENTIAL OF CUBOSOMES:**CUBOSOMES AS DIAGONSTIC TOOLS:****ENCAPSULATION OF CONTRAST AGENTS:**

One of the most successful approaches for clinical detection and prognostic surveillance is magnetic resonance imaging. A non-invasive imaging technique that offers extensive multi-parametric data, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is typically utilised for brain imaging. A contrast agent that can give dynamic vascular/perfusional attributes to tissues and a better representation of massive and medium-sized vassals is favourable for MRI.^{8,9} In MRI, gadolinium (Gd)-based contrast agents are frequently utilised. For targeted image-guided drug delivery, a large variety of Gd-based liposomal MRI contrast agents have been created.¹⁰ One of the key benefits of chemical exchange saturation transfer MRI is its capacity to identify diamagnetic substances that traditional MRI is unable to detect.¹¹ It enables the direct, high-resolution MRI detection of a wide range of bioorganic agents, nanocarriers, and natural substances. For image-guided medication delivery, it is beneficial.¹²

FLUROSCENCE IMAGING:

Fluorescence imaging has exceptional sensitivity for detecting molecular interactions and expression levels. Research has examined various approaches of NP functionalisation to improve fluorescence imaging. Biological tissues are imaged using a functionalised nanoprobe and a high fluorescence microscopy. Tryptophan absorbs and emits UV light, making it suitable for deep ultraviolet imaging. Multiphoton imaging (MPI) reduces signal to noise ratio by minimising autofluorescence, as biomolecules have a low two photon cross section.¹³

QUANTUM DOTS:

Quantum dots are nanoscale semiconductor crystals with diameters typically less than 10 nm that display unique quantum confinement characteristics.¹⁴ Because of their zero-dimensional structure, they have discrete, quantified energy states that differ from bulk materials.

This results in size-dependent optical and electrical properties, allowing the emission and absorption

spectra to be accurately controlled.¹⁵ Their remarkable photoluminescence, great brightness, narrow emission bands, and superior photostability as compared to organic dyes make them extremely valuable. QDs are frequently used in optoelectronics (light-emitting diodes, lasers, and solar cells), as well as biological imaging and diagnostics. Their capacity to emit many colours simultaneously under a single wavelength illumination improves multiplexed detection in biology.¹⁶ Thus, quantum dots are an important family of nanomaterials that connect fundamental physics with sophisticated applications in energy, electronics, and medicine.¹⁷

CUBOSOMES AS THERAPEUTIC NANOCARRIERS:

CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC DELIVERY:

Cubosomes may increase the solubility, stability, and targeted administration of chemotherapy agents that are poorly soluble in water, and their role in chemotherapeutic drug delivery has grabbed researchers' attention.¹⁸ Cubosomes' unusual internal nanostructure, consisting of a lipid bilayer organised in a bicontinuous cubic phase with interconnected water channels, permits for the simultaneous encapsulation of hydrophilic and hydrophobic anticancer medicines. This allows for the effective implementation of co-delivery systems and combination therapy to treat cancer while combating multidrug resistance.¹⁹

Cubosomes improve the therapeutic efficacy of chemotherapeutic medications by allowing for regulated and sustained drug release, reducing systemic toxicity, and increasing accumulation in cancer tissues through the increased permeability and retention (EPR) mechanism. In addition, surface modification with targeting ligands (such as folic acid, peptides, and antibodies) enables active targeting of cancer cells, resulting in improved intracellular uptake.²⁰

Numerous anticancer medications have been effectively incorporated into cubosomes for preclinical and experimental use. For example, as compared to free doxorubicin, doxorubicin-loaded cubosomes have shown decreased cardiotoxicity and increased cytotoxicity. Cubosomes loaded with

curcumin and paclitaxel have also demonstrated enhanced bioavailability and tumour suppression in both in vitro and in vivo settings. Cubosomes have also been investigated for co-delivery systems, such as mixing gene-silencing drugs or photosensitisers with chemotherapeutics to provide synergistic effects.²¹

Figure: 3 Chemotherapeutic Delivery of Cubosomes

CISPLATIN:

Cisplatin, an alkylating agent and platinum (II) analogue, creates DNA adducts by causing DNA strands to cross-link, preventing DNA repair, and triggering cancer cell death. It is frequently used to treat solid tumours and works particularly well against ovarian and testicular malignancies that have spread.²² Zhang and colleagues used the HepG2 liver cancer cell line to study cisplatin-loaded cubosomes, both uncoated and poly- ϵ -coated. According to cytotoxicity experiments, the cubosome formulations of cisplatin were less harmful than free cisplatin. Because of burst release, uncoated cubosomes were more hazardous, whereas coated cubosomes had cell viability that was almost identical to that of blank cubosomes. This suggests that coating efficiently reduces toxicity by regulating drug release.²³

METHOTREXATE:

Methotrexate (MTX), a potent folate antagonist in the antimetabolites class, is used to treat a wide range of cancers (leukaemia, lung, breast, head and neck, skin, and uterine), as well as autoimmune ailments like psoriasis and rheumatoid arthritis. MTX suppresses

dihydrofolate reductase, inhibiting dihydrofolate from being turned into tetrahydrofolate, which is needed for thymidine and DNA synthesis. Janakiraman et al. synthesised methotrexate-loaded cubosomes (MTCs 1-8) with varying concentrations of Poloxamer 188, cetyl palmitate, and water.²⁴

GENE DELIVERY:

Cubosomes has distinct nanostructure, biocompatibility, and capacity to efficiently transport and preserve nucleic acids have drawn more and more attention to their potential in gene delivery applications. Cubosomes are lipid-based nanoparticles that are ideal for loading hydrophilic nucleic acids as well as hydrophobic adjuvants or cofactors because of their internal bicontinuous cubic phase, which is made up of a lipid bilayer and interconnecting water channels.²⁵

Protecting and delivering genetic information to cells while preventing enzymatic breakdown and inadequate cellular absorption is one of the main issues in gene therapy. By enclosing genetic material in their internal aqueous network, protecting it from nucleases, and promoting cellular absorption through endocytosis.²⁶ Targeting and transfection efficiency can be enhanced by cubosome surface modification. For example, cationic polymers or surfactants might modify the surface of cubosomes, allowing them to engage electrostatically with negatively charged DNA or RNA molecules. Targeting ligands, such as transferrin, can also be integrated into cubosome surfaces to improve targeted delivery to specific cell types, such as immune cells or cancer. As an example, siRNA-loaded cubosomes targeting oncogenes have demonstrated promising gene silencing effectiveness in cancer cell lines.²⁷ The use of pluronic block copolymers to improve immunisation during DNA vaccination was a unique gene therapy technique. However, encoding DNA with proteins such as fibroblast growth factor, endothelial growth factors, interleukin-5, and erythropoietin produced rather modest expression levels, but transport of bare DNA to skeletal muscle demonstrated some gene expression. The efficiency of other delivery systems that employed cationic DNA and poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) was limited by DNA condensation. To overcome this, plasmid DNA was mixed with

pluronic block copolymers, which increased gene expression 5 to 20 fold over bare DNA without resulting in DNA condensation. The 0.01% w/v concentration that produced the best gene expression also preserved a 500 fold safety margin in animal experiments. In DNA vaccination, this approach offers a viable and secure substitute for improving gene delivery and expression.²⁸

PHOTOTHERMAL AND PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY USING ENCAPSULATED AGENTS:

PDT has already established itself in clinical healthcare, combining various advantages such as low invasiveness, high efficiency, and controllability. The PDR of type-I PDT involves electron/hydrogen transfer between triplet state (T₁)-PSs and oxygen, producing lethal ROS such as superoxide anion (O₂^{•-}), hydroxyl radical (•OH), and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O). In contrast, type-II PDT's PDR involves energy transfer from T₁ state-PSs to triplet oxygen, resulting in the creation of singlet oxygen, which promotes cell necrosis and death. The most studied type of PDT is Type-II, which treats diseased tissues with 10² reactive and oxidising molecules. This species has high electrophilia and can efficiently oxidise components such as unsaturated fatty acids, nucleic acids, proteins, and mitochondrial membranes, causing cancer cell death.²⁹

PTT has great potential in the treatment of tumours. PTT involves using a near-infrared (NIR) laser to illuminate a tumour either topically or interstitially via an optical fibre. Optical absorption transforms light energy into heat. The PTT protocol determines whether the target tissue is partially or completely ablated over time. Selective photothermal absorbers can effectively target difficult-to-treat tumours with little invasiveness. Advanced cancers can be treated by using partially-ablated tumours to stimulate the immune system and provide tumour antigens.³⁰

SURFACE FUNCTIONALIZATION:

Enhancing cubosome stability, biocompatibility, and targeting capabilities by surface functionalisation with polymers, ligands, or other functional groups allows for effective drug administration. Numerous methods have been devised to immobilise functions on the surface of nanoparticles; they may be broadly

divided into different groups: covalent conjugation and non-covalent interactions.³¹

The functionalised component polymer is chemically immobilised and bonded to the surface of nanoparticles using the widely used covalent conjugation process. Functional groups must be present on the surface in order for functionalised moieties to adhere. Nucleic acids, amines, thiols, alcohols, and maleimides are only a few examples of functional groups immobilised on nanoparticle surfaces.³²

Noncovalent interactions demonstrate the adaptability of surface functionalisation strategies by providing an additional pathway for ligand attachment. This technique depends on the interaction of attractive forces, including as van der Waals forces, hydrophobic contacts, hydrogen bonds, and electrostatic interactions, between the surfaces of nanoparticles and functionalised moieties.³³ Electrostatic interactions between negatively charged substances can also result in stable ligand immobilisation. Electrostatic interactions that employ the intrinsic electrical properties of ligands and nanoparticles can cause effective surface modification. Physical adsorption is mediated by the formation of hydrogen bonds or hydrophobic forces, also provides a non-invasive method for ligand attachment. For example, in interactions with hydrophobic molecules, hydrophobically modified dextran is physically adsorbed onto the surface of polystyrene nanostructures. Nanoparticle technology stabilisation in biological specimens is important for enhancing drug bioavailability and reducing toxicity.³⁴ Nanoparticle surface alteration materials can be roughly divided into polysaccharides or microscopic molecules, with each having distinct advantages depending on the requirements of the application. The fundamental factor used to distinguish macromolecules from tiny molecules is the mass of the molecules. Macromolecules are molecules with a high molecular weight, often greater than 1 kDa. These molecules are usually huge, complicated structures formed when monomers are polymerised via covalent bonds.³⁵

The interactions between nanoparticles are temporarily blocked by polymeric ligands. There have

been many other kinds of polymeric ligands employed, but PEG is the most widely used due to its popularity and biocompatibility. The hydrophilic properties of PEG provide even another justification for its use. The hydration layer that PEG creates around the nanoparticles creates a repulsive force that stops particles from clumping together. Nanoparticle stability in biological fluids is improved by this steric stabilisation. Additionally, PEG decreases the propensity of particles to agglomerate, increasing the durability of polymeric nanoparticles in aqueous dispersions and during storage.³⁶

POLYSACCHARIDES:

A Cell-to-cell communication depends on polysaccharides, also known as glycans, which are molecules that attach to proteins preferentially. Glycans have the crucial ability to remain selective for particular cell types via their carbohydrate receptors, independent of the media in which they are employed. The complicated chemical process on the nanoparticles' surface is the drawback of this process approach. The steric protection of polysaccharides, which inhibits protein adsorption and macrophage absorption, is what gives them their stabilising effect when they are sprayed onto the surface of nanoparticles.³⁷

LIGANDS:

The nanoparticles are stabilised by tiny molecules like ligands, surfactants, and small organic compounds by a variety of processes such as altering surface charge or lowering surface tension. The stability, simplicity of conjugation with nanoparticles, and affordability of small molecules make them superior to macromolecules when used as the targeted ligand. The inability to effectively identify tiny compounds as targeted ligands and their decreased specificity and affinity for target cell surface receptors are among the disadvantages of using them.³⁸

APPLICATION IN PRECISION MEDICINE:

Figure: 4 Application of precision medicine

CANCER THERNOSTICS:

Chemotherapeutic medications have several downsides, including major side effects and minimal effectiveness in therapy. Nanomedicines aid in the metabolic and targeted retention of chemotherapeutic treatments, providing for a better balance of therapy efficacy and toxicity.³⁹ Many nanomedicines, including liposomes, polymer-drug conjugates, and polymeric assemblies, have been investigated over the years to improve tumor-targeted drug delivery. These nanomedicines use both passive and active targeting, and triggered release mechanisms. Recently, nanoscale biomaterial-driven technologies have overcome a variety of complicated and robust scientific and technological challenges.⁴⁰

Nanoscale biomaterial-based solutions have recently solved a number of tough scientific and technological challenges. Smart nanomaterials improve cancer detection sensitivity and selectivity while having fewer side effects than traditional techniques.⁴¹ The novel nanomaterials system in cancer treatment targets the tumour microenvironment (TME) and neutralises remnants in standard cells, reducing side effects and toxicity. Nanomaterials improve therapeutic effectiveness by improving sensitivity, light absorption, half-life, and solubility, while also confirming drug discharge over time.⁴²

Figure: 5 Diagramtic Representation of Cancer Thernosticss

CARDIOVASCULAR THERNOSTICS:

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a broad category of conditions that affect the heart and blood vessels, including plaque accumulation, cardiomyopathy, ventricular fibrillation, infarction of the myocardium, coronary artery disease, ruptured arteries, and high blood pressure. These diseases are usually associated with vascular blockages, reduced myocardial function, irregular cardiac rhythms, and dilation of the cardiomyopathy, which all contribute to a significant amount of mortality and morbidity worldwide. CVDs are predicted to account for the majority of NCD-related deaths by 2025. According to the most recent data from 2017, CVDs killed 17.7 million people. CVDs account for nearly one-third of all mortality worldwide, emphasising their severity. A number of physiological aspects must be taken into account when developing and designing theranostic nanomaterials for the treatment of atherosclerosis. Fibrin is a feasible biomarker for diagnosing atherosclerotic plaques since it is highly sensitive during plaque formation. In contrast with fibrin, $\alpha v \beta 3$ integrin is a distinct biomarker associated with angiogenesis. Cardiovascular imaging has shown that statins and PKSK9 inhibitors can effectively stabilise and reduce atherosclerosis. Cardiovascular imaging can predict the efficacy of pharmacological drugs on clinical outcomes and patient responsiveness.⁴³

Figure: 6 Diagrammatic representation of Cardiovascular Theranostics

NEUROLOGICAL DISORDER:

Theranostics revolutionises neurological disease therapy by integrating focused diagnostics with personalised therapies. Theranostic devices provide continuous surveillance of disease progression in conditions such as Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's, cerebral tumours, and schizophrenia while simultaneously administering therapeutic drugs. ⁴³ When paired with advanced imaging techniques, nanotechnology-based technologies such as cubosomes and quantum dots improve the barrier between blood and brain penetration and allow for precise medicine distribution. This multiple effectiveness makes more feasible to detect complications early, improve treatment, and assess therapeutic outcomes. Importantly, theranostics minimises off-target toxic effects, which is critical in fragile brain tissues. ⁴⁴ Theranostics holds promise for accuracy in neurology by combining molecular imaging with targeted medicines, resulting in increased efficacy, fewer side effects, and a path to truly customised treatment solutions for catastrophic neurological disorders. ⁴⁵

Figure: 7 Molecular mechanisms contributing to the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative disease

FUTURE ASPECTS :

Cubosome-based theranostics has the potential to transform precision medicine by merging diagnosis and therapy into a single, smart nanocarrier. Advancements will concentrate on personalised medicine, in which cubosome formulations are tailored to individual patients based on genetic and molecular profiles, with artificial intelligence assisting in the prediction of optimal compositions, medication ratios, and target techniques. ⁴⁶ Multi-modal imaging capabilities will be improved by integrating agents for MRI, PET and fluorescence into the same cubosome, allowing for real-time tracking and therapeutic response. Stimuli-responsive cubosomes will form and release their payload in response to tumor-specific triggers such as pH changes, reactive oxygen species, or overexpressed enzymes, as well as external stimuli like near-infrared light, ultrasound, or magnetic fields. These systems will also facilitate combination therapy, delivering chemotherapeutics, photothermal/photodynamic medicines, and potentially gene-editing tools such as siRNA or CRISPR-C alongside imaging probes to provide full disease management. Future designs will emphasise natural, biodegradable lipids for safety, with self-destructing systems that dissolve after serving their purpose. ⁴⁷ Integration with wearable and implantable devices will allow for real-time, regulated drug release based on patient vitals. Beyond oncology, theranostic cubosomes will have implications in neurological, cardiovascular, and viral illnesses, providing early identification and focused treatment. Clinical implementation will be accelerated by regulatory improvements, such as

standardised GMP methods and the use of FDA-approved lipid components. Overall, the future of cubosomal theranostics is in building multifunctional, patient-specific, environmentally friendly systems that can give precise diagnosis and therapy from a single, intelligent platform.⁴⁸

Figure: 8 Future Aspects of Theranostics in Cubosomes

CONCLUSION:

Cubosomes act as a next-generation nanocarrier system with distinct structural, physicochemical, and functional attributes, making them ideal for theranostic applications. Their dual drug imaging capacity, flexible surface changes, and controlled release profiles provide effective illness detection, targeted therapy, and real-time monitoring. In oncology, they have shown improved therapeutic efficacy while reducing systemic toxicity; in cardiovascular and neurological illnesses, they provide new potential for early detection and personalised treatments. Emerging technologies including stimuli-responsive designs, multimodal imaging integration, and AI-assisted formulation optimisation expand their clinical utility. However, problems with scalability, long-term stability, and demanding regulatory norms must be resolved before widespread implementation. Future research ought to emphasise biodegradable lipids, eco-friendly synthesis, and patient-specific formulations to enable clinical translation. Overall, cubosome-enabled theranostics has the potential to redefine precision medicine by delivering safe, effective, and intelligent nanoplateforms for simultaneous diagnosis and therapy.

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